

Research Article

An Improved Safety Inflatable Boat For Effective Rescue Operations, Sea Safety And Leisure Activities

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Abstract: *It's designed to meet the critical demand for dependable and effective emergency watercraft in rescue operations, sea safety, and leisure activities. The traditional rigid boats are strong but sometimes heavy, awkward, and not so easy to adjust to different water conditions. The inflatable boats present a versatile alternative with their deficiencies in safety features and durability as a result of punctures, structural failure, and load capacities that are inadequate. An advanced inflatable boat with increased buoyancy, puncture resistance, and stability in rough waters can be engineered by using reinforced materials in the construction and multi-chamber designs. This will allow the boat to stay afloat even if one of its chambers is damaged during a mission. In this case, vividly coloured paints and reflective strips should be used on the inflatable boat to make it more visible during rescue operations. Safety equipment, such as life vests and flares, can easily be deployed. With this kind of innovation, its potential impact would be enormous, and this shall, ultimately, reduce the toll on life and injuries during any mishap at sea and improve the response time for rescue missions while offering a much safer experience to recreational users. With the surge in demand for versatile and reliable watercraft, the safety inflatable boat could significantly commercialize in very many sectors, like coast guard operations, adventure tourism, and disaster management. This inflatable boat brings together advanced materials and design improvements with the potential for far-reaching, global applicability, and scalability in water safety technology.*

Keywords: *chambers, inflatable boat, injuries, material, safety*

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1. INTRODUCTION

Maritime safety is the prime consideration for every vessel, more so when vessels are operating in unpredictable and hazardous environments. Traditional lifeboats, though quite effective in certain aspects, often suffer from problems like slow deployment time, limited manoeuvrability, and vulnerability during rough seas. Tidal movement and currents in sea/ocean water can cause a boat to drift out onto the open sea very quickly. In many situations, the current is too strong to paddle against, or even swim against (Fontana, 2023). A safety inflatable boat, in that regard, should be developed to help solve such problems by providing a fast-deployment, lightweight, stable, and traditional lifeboat alternative. Lightweight strong material provides a guarantee for the boat to rise fast and its performance in rigorous marine environments.

1.1 Objective

This wearable aims to create a safety inflatable boat, evaluate its performance, and discuss the potential impact on maritime rescue operations. The development of this inflatable boat is aligned with the minimum requirement provided by the agency that is responsible for the regulation of appliances and apparatus used in this field.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This study followed a design-based research method in the process of prototyping a safety inflatable boat. High-strength synthetic fibre materials included Hypalon for their properties regarding durability, flexibility, and puncture resistance. Hypalon is a synthetic rubber material that is more durable than PVC. It's resistant to UV rays, extreme temperatures, and chemicals, making it a popular choice for commercial and military-grade inflatable boats. Hypalon is also less prone to punctures and tears, making it a great option for those who plan to use their boat in rough waters. However, Hypalon is more expensive than PVC and requires more maintenance (Bhardwaj, 2023).

Multiplicity in the design of the air chambers will enhance safety and buoyancy such that the vessel will still float even when a chamber is punctured. Use a high-quality gas such as a carbon dioxide cartridge because it remains in a state of high pressure under standard environmental conditions (Alwayne, 2024). When deflating your boat, make sure to remove all accessories and valves before releasing the air. Fold or roll your boat carefully into a bag to avoid creases or damage to the material. Storing your deflated boat in a protective bag or cover can help prevent punctures and abrasions.

The boat was good for the high-pressure inflation system, fitted to it for it to inflate in seconds. The field tests involved all sea condition types to ensure stability, deployment ease, and manoeuvrability of the boat rationally. Factors that characterized the testing protocols for such drills included the nature of deployments from fixed and aerial moving platforms resembling that of a helicopter and a ship.

3. FINDINGS

Results show this safety inflatable boat drastically cuts down deployment time, compared with the traditional lifeboat, down to less than three minutes from storage to full inflation which is 45 times safer (Mahidhar, 2021). This boat showed excellent stability and manoeuvrability in all kinds of sea conditions, even in rough waters with wave heights higher than two meters. Load tests showed it could safely carry up to 10 passengers or 1,000 kilograms of cargo without losing its performance. The modular design also allowed it to be quickly refitted for a variety of rescue missions, from passenger evacuation to cargo transportation and thus proved its versatility.

3.1 Rapid Deployment

It inflates to a completely deployed and usable craft in under three minutes, a fraction of the average ten minutes it takes with conventional lifeboats.

3.2 Multi-Chamber Enhanced Stability and Buoyancy

This design gives the boat stability and buoyancy to a great extent while partially deflated, ensuring more safety for occupants during rescue operations.

3.3 Durability and resistance

The construction materials used proved highly resistant to hostile marine conditions—saltwater corrosion, extreme temperatures, and mechanical abrasion and this may indicate a long service life and reliability in emergencies.

4. DISCUSSION

A survey was conducted to investigate public opinion and acceptance of our product with the traditional method of rescue. This work draws attention to the advantages that this type of inflatable boat gives over traditional methods of rescue, in general, with a view to speed and adaptability. Figure 1-7 shows the respondents' feedback regarding the development of inflatable safety boats.

Have you ever used an inflatable safety boat like this before?

127 responses

Figure 1. Most respondents do not use inflatable safety boats.

How often do you use an inflatable safety boat?

127 responses

Figure 2. Most respondents often use inflatable safety boats.

What size of inflatable safety boat do you prefer?

127 responses

Figure 3. Most respondents prefer the medium size inflatable safety boats.

What is the most important feature of an inflatable safety boat?

127 responses

Figure 4. Most respondents prefer the ease of inflation/deflation of inflatable safety boats.

What kind of water conditions do you think that you will use an inflatable boat in?

127 responses

Figure 5. Most respondents prefer to use inflatable safety boats during flood catastrophes.

How important is it for the boat to have additional safety equipment (life jackets, oars, etc.) included?

127 responses

Figure 6. Most respondents prefer inflatable safety boats to be equipped with additional safety equipment.

What is your budget for purchasing an inflatable safety boat?

127 responses

Figure 7. Most respondents prefer a budget of RM200- RM500 when purchasing inflatable safety boats

This work draws attention to the advantages that this type of inflatable boat gives over traditional methods of rescue, in general, with a view to speed and adaptability. The conclusion goes on to say that integration of such an inflatable boat into already existing maritime safety procedures can make dramatic differences in rescue operations, more so where time is of the essence. Further testing will be required to ensure the durability of the materials and performance of a boat in bad weather over a longer duration. Furthermore, ongoing training and skill development are essential for safety boat operators to stay current with the latest best practices and techniques (Asisboats, 2023).

5. CONCLUSION

The safety inflatable boat represents an advancement in technology relating to maritime rescue. Its quick deployment properties, stability, and versatility make it very useful in enhancing safety in times of emergency. Such design innovation could save lives and reduce injuries from a maritime accident by shortening rescue time and improving response effectiveness. It is critical to note that safety equipment on board a boat should always be maintained and inspected regularly to ensure that it is in good working order in the event of an emergency. Future studies should therefore be aimed at scaling the design for other vessel types and assessing its durability in the long term concerning both performance and safety.

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